
Effects of Different Sowing Media on Germination of Australian Pine Tree
(*Casuarina incana* Benth.)

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Abstract

Casuarina incana is an important tree species. However, poor germination and inadequate silvicultural information are important factors militating against its regeneration. Therefore, this study is aimed at determining the effects of different sowing media on germination of *C. incana* with a view of knowing the best sowing media for raising *C. incana*. The experiment was arranged in a completely Randomized Design (CRD) with three replicates. Viable seeds were sown into germination sieving baskets filled with four sowing media (Topsoil, sawdust, clay soil and river sand). Fifty seeds were sown into each germination sieving baskets. Data were collected on germination percentage. Analysis of variance was used to analyze the data collected. Means separation were carried out using the Least Significant Difference (LSD). The result revealed that germination percentage was significant at 5% level of probability. The highest germination percentage was recorded for treatment B (Sawdust) which had $3.75 \pm 30\%$ while treatments A (Topsoil) and D (River sand) had $3.56 \pm 28.5\%$ and $3.25 \pm 26\%$ respectively. The least was treatment C (Clay soil) which had $3.19 \pm 25.5\%$. but there was no significant difference in germination percentage of *C. incana*. The study has shown that the germination percentage of *C. incana* improved significantly with sowing media especially sawdust and topsoil. The use of sawdust and topsoil as sowing media for small and large scale propagation of the species is recommended.

Keywords: Seeds, Germination, Media, *Casuarina incana*, Growth

Received: 20/08/18

Accepted: 29/11/18

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ISSN: 2141 - 4203 Science and Education Development Inst., Nigeria

Introduction

Germination is the resumption of active embryo growth after a dormant period. The seed must be viable (the embryo must be alive and capable of germination). Low seed germination (vigor) is a function of the age and storage conditions of the planted seed as well as the health and maturity of the plant from which the seed was harvested. Internal conditions of the seed must be favorable for germination, that is, any physical, chemical, or physiological barriers to germination must have disappeared or must have been removed. The seed must be subjected to appropriate environmental conditions, including water (moisture), proper temperature, oxygen, and for some species, light. Forest-tree seeds have different germination rates and optimal temperatures.

Moisture is one essential condition for seed germination, and poor germination is very costly to growers. There is, nevertheless, little experimental evidence concerning the effects of different percentages of available moisture (Anber, 2010) on germination; more study of the subject is essential. Since most forest-tree seeds are planted at shallow depths, there may be rapid fluctuations of soil moisture around the seed, especially during the warmer months. This condition is common both to the irrigated soils of the west and to the soils of humid areas. Though several reports have been published concerning the effect of soil moisture upon germination, in no case has there been accurate measurement of the available soil moisture. Avery (2002) indicates that seed germination varies with the species of plant concerned as well as with the percentage of soil moisture. According to Dickens (2011), several species of forest-tree seeds respond differently to various amounts of supplementary water in addition to natural rainfall. Ibrahim (2004), studying the germination of New Zealand spinach, found it to be variable; but the germination was increased when the seeds were dried at intervals during the tests. McCork (2004) studied the combined effects of soil moisture and fertilizer placement on the germination of cabbage, snap beans, and pea seeds. In some treatments there were indications that low soil moisture and method of fertilizer application reduced germination. McDonald (2003) has studied the effect of soil moisture, temperature, and varieties of wheat upon germination. Germination was affected by these three factors. As Okunomo (2010) has shown, the seeds of several plant species will absorb water from solutions much higher in atmospheric pressure than 16 atmospheres (Takayama, 2005) which is approximately the pressure of the permanent wilting percentage (Anber, 2010). Xanthium seed proved able to extract water from a solution whose concentration was 1,000 atmospheres. Therefore, the study is aimed at determining the effects of different sowing media on

germination of *C. incana* with a view of knowing the best sowing media for raising *C. incana* at both germination and nursery stage.

Materials and Methods

Experimental Site

The experiment was carried out in Nursery C of the Federal College of Forestry, Ibadan. The College is situated at Jericho Hill, Ibadan North West Local Government Area of Oyo State. The area lies between Latitude 7°26'N and Longitude 3°54'E. The annual rainfall ranges from 1400mm - 1500mm and average relative humidity of about 65%, the average temperature is 31.8°C.

Seeds Source

The seeds of *C. incana* were purchased at the Forestry Research Institute (FRIN), Jericho, Ibadan.

Experimental Design and Treatment Procedure

The design used in this experiment was a Completely Randomized Design (CRD). The study involved the use of four (4) sowing media with three (3) replicates. The treatments were topsoil, sawdust, clay soil and river sand. Fifty (50) seeds were raised each for the different sowing media and a total of 200 seeds were used for the study. The seeds were broadcast in sieving baskets containing the different sowing media and kept in a humidified environment. The sieving baskets were watered daily. At the end of the germination experiment, 12 seedlings were randomly selected per sowing media, and transplanted into polythene pots. Each polythene pot was regarded as individual replicate.

Assessment of Growth Parameters

Daily observations were made to determine the effects of the four sowing media on the germination of seeds of *C. incana*. Germination recordings were discontinued and considered to have been completed when no additional germination took place in five weeks. The production of new leaves was recorded by visual counting number of leaves produced weekly.

Data Analysis

Data collected on germinations were analyzed using analysis of variance (ANOVA) in a Completely Randomized Design. Percentage seed germination was calculated as:

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ISSN: 2141 - 4203 Science and Education Development Inst., Nigeria

% germination = $\frac{x}{y} \times 100$ 1

Where;

x = number of seeds germinated

y = number of seeds sown

Results and Discussion

Seed Germination

The result on effect of four (4) different sowing media on the germination of *C. incana* is shown in Table 1. The result shows that the highest mean germination percentage was recorded for treatment B (Sawdust) which had 3.75±30%. Treatment A (Topsoil) and D (River sand) had 3.56±28.5% and 3.25±26% respectively. The least was treatment C (Clay soil) which had 3.19±25.5%. The mean germination percentage of the species with the four sowing media were statistically not different at 5% level of significance with a value of 0.238 as presented in Table 2.

Table 1: Mean germination percentage of *C. incana* using different sowing media

Treatment	Mean S.E	± 95% confidence interval for mean		Minimum	Maximum
		Lower bound	Upper bound		
A (Topsoil)	3.56±0.21	2.88	4.24	3.00	4.00
B (Sawdust)	3.75±0.23	3.02	4.48	3.25	4.25
C (Clay Soil)	3.19±0.06	2.99	3.39	3.00	3.25
D (River Sand)	3.25±0.27	2.39	4.11	2.75	4.00

Where; S.E = Standard error

Table 2: Analysis of variance (ANOVA) for germination percentage

	Sum of Square	DF	Mean Square	F	Sig.
Between Treatments	0.844	3	0.281	1.612	0.238
Within Treatments	2.094	12	0.174		
Total	2.938	15			

Conclusion

The study has shown that the germination percentage of *C. incana* improved significantly with sowing media especially sawdust and topsoil. This will play an important role in ensuring uniform and maximum germination of the species in the nursery and any subsequent afforestation or re-vegetation programme using the species stand successful. This result will be most useful to forest nursery practitioners and other scientists working for sustainable management of this species.

References

- Anber M. A. Hassanein (2010). Improving seed germination and seedling growth of some economically important trees by seed. *Forest Sci.*, 7(3): 371-382.
- Avery, T. E. and Burkhart, H. E. (2002). Forest management. 5th Ed. McGraw-Hill Higher Education. New York, USA p. 408.
- Dickens Dolor (2011). Effect of propagation media on the germination and seedling performance of *Irovingia wimbolu* (Vermoesen). *American Journal Biotechnology and Molecular Sciences*. doi:10525/ajbms.2011.1.2.51.56.
- Ibrahim, A., and Otegbeye, G. O. (2004). Method of Achieving Optimum Germination in *Adasonia digitata*. *Bowen J. Agric* 1:177-182.
- McCork, J.K. (2004). Principles and practices of seed harvesting process and storage: an organic seed production manual for seed growers. Creative commons, Stanford California 94305, USA, p.28.
- McDonald, I., Omoruyi, O. (2003). Effect of seed pre-treatment on germination of two surface types of *Dialium guineensis*. *Seed Technol.* 25:41-44.
- Okunomo, K. (2010). Germination and Seedling growth of *Parkia bicolor* (A. Cheu) as influenced by nursery techniques. *African Journal of General Agriculture*. Vol.6. No. 4.
- Takayama, S., Isogai, A (2005). "Self-incompatibility in plants". *Annu Rev Plant Biol.* 56:467-87. DOI:10. 1146/annurev.arplant.56.032604. 144249. PMID 15862104.
- Wikipedia (2012). www.wikipedia.com the free encyclopedia.